

Two new records of octopods in Canary Islands: *Amphioctopus burryi* (Voss, 1950) and *Macrotritopus defilippi* (Vérany, 1851) [Cephalopoda: Octopodidae]

Dos nuevos registros de pulpos en las islas Canarias: *Amphioctopus burryi* (Voss, 1950) and *Macrotritopus defilippi* (Vérany, 1851) [Cephalopoda: Octopodidae]

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports two species of octopods from the Canary Islands for the first time: *Amphioctopus burryi*, and *Macrotritopus defilippi*. Two specimens, one for each species, were caught by scuba diving in Tenerife Island. Morphological and morphometric characteristics and information on habitat, biology and geographical distribution of the two species are given. The specimen of *M. defilippi* was filmed. In a 17 seconds video record the animal displayed a "flamboyant pattern" while walking on the substrate supported on its arms fleeing the diver. As far as we know, this is the first time that the species is filmed in its natural habitat.

RESUMEN

En este artículo se reportan por primera vez dos nuevos registros de pulpos en las Islas Canarias: *Amphioctopus burryi*, and *Macrotritopus defilippi*. Se capturó un ejemplar de cada especie mediante buceo autónomo en la isla de Tenerife. Se proporciona información sobre el hábitat, biología y distribución geográfica de ambas especies. El ejemplar de *M. defilippi* fue filmado, y, en un registro de video de 17 segundos, mostró una "pauta llamativa" mientras caminaba sobre el sustrato apoyado sobre sus brazos tratando de huir del buceador. Hasta donde conocemos, esta es la primera vez que se filma la especie en su medio natural.

INTRODUCTION

The Canary Islands were not included in the first review of the cephalopods for the Iberian Peninsula (GUERRA, 1992). The reason was that this archipelago lies outside the Western Mediterranean Sea and the Mediterranean outflow faunistic provinces defined by BAKUS, HAEDRICH

AND ROBINSON (1977), which were the ones considered in that review. Nevertheless, the octopod species *Macrotritopus defilippi* (as *Octopus defilippi*) was recorded in the Iberian Peninsula waters (GUERRA, 1992; GUERRA AND ROCHA, 2011). Afterwards, that species and *Amphioctopus*

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Table I. Biometric data of *A. burryi* and *M. defilippi* off the Canary Islands. TL: total length (mm), DML: dorsal mantle length (mm), VML: ventral mantle length (mm), HL: head length (mm), HW: head width (mm), FL: funnel length (mm), FW: funnel width (mm), ALI-IV: arm length I-IV (mm), LL: Ligula length (mm), W: Weight (g), S: Sex.

Tabla I. Datos biométricos de *A. burryi* y *M. defilippi* de las Islas Canarias. TL: longitud total (mm); DML: longitud dorsal del manto (mm); VML: longitud ventral del manto (mm); HL: longitud de la cabeza (mm); HW: anchura de la cabeza (mm); FL: longitud del sifón (mm); FW: anchura del sifón (mm); ALI-IV: longitud de los brazos (mm); LL: longitud de la ligula (mm); P: peso total (g), S: sexo.

	<i>A. burryi</i>	<i>M. defilippi</i>	Observations
TL	210	430	
DML	66	41	
VML	40	27	
HL	21	19	Dorsal
HW	20	13	Dorsal
FL	18	11	
FW	12	9	
ALI	120 (115)	107 (141)	Left (Right)
ALII	136 (128)	160 (159)	"
ALIII	132 (137)	328 (159)	"
ALIV	133 (128)	230 (256)	"
LL	—	3	
W	50,2	15,0	
S	Female	Male	

burryi were also not included in the catalogue of marine species for the Canary Islands because they were not reliably recorded in this archipelago (GUERRA, HERNÁNDEZ AND DOMÍNGUEZ, 2003). Recently, both species are considered present in the Canary Islands in the FAO guide for Atlantic African waters cephalopod species. The reason for this was that the first author (A.G) had news of these records during the correction of the last version of that guide (GUERRA, GONZÁLEZ, JEREB AND ROELEVELD, in press).

After the Hawaiian Islands, the Canary Islands are probably the best studied volcanic island system in the world, both in terms of their geological history and the phylogenetic origin of their biota (see SANMARTIN, VAN DER MARK AND RONQUIST, 2008 and the references therein). Within the Macaronesian province, the marine life found in the Canary Islands is interesting, being a combination of North Atlantic, Mediterranean, and endemic species. Although the list of marine species of other groups of mollusks is relatively

long (MORO, MARTÍN, GARRIDO AND IZQUIERDO, 2003), the teuthofauna of this archipelago only comprise 80 species and only 6 of them are incirrate octopods (GUERRA, GONZÁLEZ, JEREB AND ROELEVELD, 2003). In recent years, the increasing popularity of both scuba diving and underwater photography has provided biologists with much new information about the marine life of the islands.

The aim of the present work is to present two new records of benthic octopods offering also the main information on their habitat, biology and geographical distribution, which are still poorly known.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Two specimens were caught in the waters of the island of Tenerife, Canary Islands during the project of the ONG Iberian Biodiversity that aims to photograph and describe the marine flora and fauna.

RESULTS

Systematics

Much of the higher classification of recent cephalopods is unstable. Various authors have suggested highly varying arrangements. We adopt the conservative arrangement followed by YOUNG, VECCHIONE AND MANGOLD (2010). On the other hand, the taxonomy of the family Octopodidae is in a thoroughly unsettled state, due to several reasons (see GUERRA ET AL. 2013). Many species previously placed in the genus *Octopus*, recently have been allocated to other genera (see NORMAN AND HOCHBERG, 2005).

Measurements and morphological characters

Table I shows the main measurements obtained for the two specimens studied. The dimensions in all cases are in millimetres (mm) and weights in grams (g). The terminology used was proposed by ROPER AND VOSS (1963). Morphological characters of the two species studied are consistent with those given by ROPER, SWEENEY AND NAUEN (1984), NESIS (1987), VOIGHT (1998), VOSS AND TOLL (1998) for *A. burryi*, and LOZANO Y REY (1905), MAGAZ (1934), ROPER ET AL. (1984), NESIS (1987), GUERRA (1992), MANGOLD (1998) for *M. defilippi*.

Family OCTOPODIDAE d'Orbigny, 1839
Subfamily OCTOPODINAE d'Orbigny, 1839
Genus *Amphioctopus* P. Fischer, 1882
Amphioctopus burryi (Voss, 1950) (Fig. 1)

Most frequent synonyms:

Octopus burryi Voss, 1950. *Revista de la Sociedad Malacológica "Carlos de la Torre"*, 7 (2): 76-79 (Type locality: Florida, USA).

Octopus vincenti Pickford, 1955. *Bull. Brit. Mus (Nat. Hist.)*, Zoology: 3(3): 151.

Material examined: Radazul, east coast of Tenerife island (28° 24' 03" N and 16° 19' 33" W), captured on May 3rd, 2011, 1 female, 210 mm in total length and 50.2 g of total weight; captured SCUBA diving at 17 m depth on sandy bottom. This species was observed on 4 out of 30 night dives made in this location during the year 2011. Preserved with formaldehyde solution 4% buffered (pH 6.9), and deposited in the collection of the Museum of Natural Sciences in Santa Cruz de Tenerife with reference TFMCBM/11309; MO/05139. María B. Caro and M.J. Sealey leg.

Diagnostic characters: Animals of small to moderate size. Up to 70 mm mantle length. Mantle, arms and head densely covered with closely set small round papillae, whose colour is dark-blue to purplish brown, forming bands along dorsolateral surface of each arm. Head moderately small. Eyes large and with a tiny papilla over each eye-ball. Funnel organ W-shaped. Moderately long arms, the third right arm (III) in male hectocotylized. The ligula is short (4 to 6% of the hectocotylized arm length). The calamus has a deep groove with around 15 small flakes. Gill lamellae 8-11 per outer demibranch. Web in side with white reticulated stripes on red background.

Habitat and biology: A benthic species taken on sandy bottoms, often covered by broken coral and shells, from 0 to 200 m on the lower part of the continental shelf. Members of this species perform fast, efficient burying manoeuvres to hide and are ambush predators. The life cycle is estimated to range from 8 to 10 months at water temperatures ranging from 22° to 25°C. Females produce about 35 000 eggs. Egg length ranges from 2 to 2.5 mm. Females carry their eggs during the embryonic development (FORSYTHE AND HANLON, 1985; HANLON AND HIXON, 1980; GUERRA, 1992).

Distribution: Tropical eastern and western Atlantic: from Georgia to the

Gulf of Mexico, Caribbean Sea and northern Brazil (VECCHIONE, 2002), and off

western Africa, Senegal and Cape Verde Islands to Angola (GUERRA ET AL., 2013).

Family OCTOPODIDAE d'Orbigny, 1839
Subfamily OCTOPODINAE d'Orbigny, 1839
Genus *Macrotritopus* Grimpe, 1922

Macrotritopus defilippi (Vérany, 1851) (Fig. 2)

Most frequent synonyms:

Octopus defilippi Vérany, 1851. *Moll. Médit.*, 1. Gênes: 30 (Type locality: Western Mediterranean Sea).

Macrotritopus kempi (Robson, 1929). *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.*, 10(3): 311-313.

Macrotritopus danae (Joubin & Robson, 1929). *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 1929(1): 89-94.

Material examined: Tabaiba, east coast of Tenerife island (28° 24' 04" N and 16° 19' 53" W), captured on May 4th, 2011, 1 male specimen, 430 mm in total length and 15.0 g total weight; captured SCUBA diving at 15 m depth on sandy bottom. The specimen was filmed. In a 17 seconds video record the animal displayed a "flamboyant pattern" (HANLON AND MESSENGER, 1996) while walking on the substrate supported on its arms fleeing the diver. The video is available in the Flickr web under the following URL <<http://flic.kr/p/ec9N2>>. As far as we know, this is the first time that the species is filmed in its natural habitat. This species was observed on 2 out of 30 night dives made in this location during the year 2011. Preserved with formaldehyde solution 4% buffered (pH 6.9), and deposited in the collection of the Museum of Natural Sciences in Santa Cruz de Tenerife with reference TFMCBM/11310; MO/05140. María B. Caro and M.J. Sealey leg.

Diagnostic characters: Animals small to moderate size, up to 90 mm mantle length; total length to about 400 mm. Small mantle in relation to total length, elongate or saccular. Funnel organ W-shaped, slender, posterior angles rounded. Very long arms, 85 to 90% of total length, slender, often conspicuously asymmetrical (each arm may be much longer than the opposite arm of same pair). Enlarged suckers absent in both sexes. Right arm III of male hectocotylized, shorter than the opposite, bears 60 to 100 suckers. Short ligula: 1.9 to 2.5% of the hectocotylized arm length. Gills with 11 lamellae per outer

demibranch. Transient papillae except over eyes. Coloured in life brown-yellow, grey brown or red-brown with dark transverse arm bars and heart-shaped pattern on dorsal mantle, often with green-iridescence, especially around eyes.

Habitat and biology: A benthic species taken on sandy and muddy bottoms. Usually it occurs from the littoral waters (about 6 m) to 200 m depth, but occasionally has been reported down to 350 m. Females lay over 10 000 eggs that may be brooded in the arms. Mature egg-size ranges between 0.9 and 1.6 mm. Larvae and

(Right page) Figure 1. *Amphioctopus burryi*, from off Radazul (Tenerife), sandy bottom at -17m. A: live specimen (1: detail of the small round papillae; 2: tiny papillae over each eye-ball; 3: dark-blue to purplish brown bands along dorsolateral surface of each arm; B: same specimen, preserved.

(Página derecha) Figura 1. *Amphioctopus burryi*, de Radazul (Tenerife), fondo arenoso en -17m. A: ejemplar vivo (1: detalle de las pequeñas papilas redondas; 2: diminutas papilas encima de cada globo ocular; 3: bandas azul oscuro hasta castaño violáceo a lo largo de la superficie dorsolateral de cada brazo; B: el mismo ejemplar, preservado.

Figure 2. *Macrotritopus defilippi*, from Tabaiba (Tenerife), sandy bottom at -15m. A: live specimen; B: the other specimen from the same locality, preserved.

Figure 2. *Macrotritopus defilippi*, de Tabaiba (Tenerife), fondo arenoso en -15m. A: ejemplar vivo; B: el otro ejemplar de la misma localidad, preservado.

juveniles are pelagic, and are characterized by extremely long ventrolateral arms. The characteristic long arms of the planktonic young seem to function in flotation, feeding, crawling and defense. No directed fisheries (HANLON, FORSYTHE AND BOLETZKY, 1985; GUERRA 1992).

Distribution: Throughout the Mediterranean Sea, Eastern Atlantic from South Portugal to South Africa, Cape Verde Islands (NESIS, 1987; GUERRA, 1992; GUERRA ET AL., 2013). Western Atlantic from the Bahamas to Brazil, in the Gulf of Mexico and the Caribbean Sea (VECCHIONE, 2002).

Remarks

The genus *Macrotritopus* needs revision. At present the only entirely described species is the one living in the Mediterranean and the eastern Atlantic, but the unresolved species of the western Atlantic are treated under the same name. The very characteristic “*Macrotritopus* larvae” have been found off South Africa and in the Indo-West Pacific, suggesting that several species may be comprised within this genus (GUERRA ET AL. in press).

Biogeography

The biogeographic model underlying ROSEN’S (1975) EP/EA distributional tracks predicts that eastern Atlantic species ought to be basal owing to the vicariant separation of the New World and eastern Atlantic faunas by the Cenozoic opening of the South Atlantic Ocean (ca. 65–95 mya; PITTMAN, CANDE, LABRECQUE AND PINDELL 1993). This would suggest that the eastern populations of *A. burryi* and *M. defilippi* would be basal, suggesting support for Rosen’s EP/EA model. However, there are many findings in marine organisms (LESSIOS, KESSING, ROBERTSON AND PAULAY 1999; MUSS, ROBERTSON, STEPIEN, WIRTZ AND

BOWEN 2001; BANFORD, BIRMINGHAM AND COLLETTE 2004) that do not fully support Rosen’s hypothesis. These findings indicate a very recent separation of trans-Atlantic species and include the possibility of dispersal playing a central role (SCHELTEMA, 1973, 1995).

Considering that *A. burryi* and *M. defilippi* have small and intermediate sized eggs, respectively and that they produce planktonic young (HOCHBERG, NIXON AND TOLL 1992), dispersion at this stage of their life cycle could be the best explanation to their present biogeography. The new hatchlings and juveniles passively transported to the south-east by the Canary Current, which is a broad region of moderate flow where the temperate waters of the Azores Current are converted into the subtropical water that feeds into the North Equatorial Current that transport water towards the East (TOMCZAK AND GODFREY, 2003). This displacement would explain the presence of these two octopods species on both sides of the Atlantic Ocean and in the Canary Islands. Nevertheless, phylogenetic analyses using New World and eastern Atlantic specimens of *A. burryi* and *M. defilippi* should be needed for assessing genetic diversification.

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